

Gravity acceleration and the angle of inclination

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We often use the words "above" and "below" without explaining these words exactly. We decide with sense organs if something is "above" or "below" from us. The position sense plays an important role. In biology there are many experiments. From biology we further know that the position sense gets stimulus through the gravitation. With that the direction of gravitation is the most important criterion for human being's orientation in space. This direction is recognized by the position sense as "below" respectively the opposite direction as "above". The direction that is recognized as "below" by the position sense is called "orientation direction" or "visual vertical".

On earth the gravitation is composed of two components. The first force is the proper gravitation and the second force is the centrifugal force resulting from earth's rotation around its axis. It is obvious to assume that the visual vertical is the resultant of gravitation and centrifugal force. This is only valid, if the angular velocity from earth's rotation around its own axis is constant or changes slowly.

We view the earth. We assume the earth is spherical.

The earth has a constant rotation time. We introduce the following quantities:

M = mass of earth
 m = mass of observer
 R = earth's radius
 α = latitude (with observer on the surface)
 w, T = angular velocity and rotation time of the planet around its own axis
 G = gravitational constant

w and T are constant. We denote the gravitation, centrifugal force, resultant force with $\vec{K}, \vec{Z}, \vec{F}$ see figure in that the parallelogram of forces is drawn. The earth's gravitation force can be calculated with Newton's law:

$$K = G \cdot \frac{Mm}{R^2}$$

The centrifugal force is $Z = mR \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot w^2$. It is $\vec{F} = \vec{K} + \vec{Z}$, see figure or with the cosine law:

$$F^2 = K^2 + Z^2 - 2KZ \cdot \cos \alpha \quad (1)$$

The gravity acceleration is $b = F/m$.

For the visual vertical the angle $\beta = \angle(\vec{F}, \vec{K})$ is interesting. We use the cosine law again:

$$Z^2 = F^2 + K^2 - 2FK \cdot \cos \beta$$

We solve to $\cos \beta$:

$$\cos \beta = \frac{F^2 + K^2 - Z^2}{2FK} \quad (2)$$

We insert equation (1) at F in equation (2):

$$\cos \beta = \frac{K^2 + Z^2 - 2KZ \cos \alpha + K^2 - Z^2}{2FK} = \frac{2K^2 - 2KZ \cos \alpha}{2FK}$$

At last we get with equation (1):

$$\cos \beta = \frac{K - Z \cdot \cos \alpha}{\sqrt{K^2 + Z^2 - 2KZ \cdot \cos \alpha}} \quad (3)$$

With the equations (1) and (3) we get F and the angle of inclination β . The planet's surface appears inclined with the angle β to one observer.

We compare the formula of the gravity acceleration with 2 further formulas that can be found in Sieber [3] p.124 und Lang [2] p.5:

$$b = (9.8063 - 0.0264 \cdot \cos 2\alpha - 0.000003 \cdot h[m]) \frac{m}{s^2} \quad (4)$$

h is the height over the earth's surface in metres. The other formula is:

$$b = 9.780327 \frac{m}{s^2} \cdot (1 + 0.0053024 \cdot \sin^2 \alpha - 0.0000058 \cdot \sin^2 2\alpha) \quad (5)$$

The same formulas without height's correction are in Allen [1] p.245. We have the following table to compare the 3 gravity accelerations and the angle of inclination:

α [degree]	angle of inclination [degree]	b (spherical model)	b (Sieber)	b (Lang)
0	0	9.7802	9.7799	9.7803
10	0.03375	9.7812	9.7815	9.7819
20	0.06341	9.7842	9.7861	9.7864
30	0.08540	9.7886	9.7931	9.7932
40	0.09706	9.7941	9.8017	9.8017
50	0.09700	9.8000	9.8109	9.8107
60	0.08525	9.8055	9.8195	9.8192
70	0.06324	9.8100	9.8265	9.8261
80	0.03363	9.8129	9.8311	9.8306
90	0	9.8139	9.8327	9.8322

We use the middle earth's radius $R=6371030m$. It is $R = \frac{2a+b}{3}$ with the equatorial radius a and the polar radius b . If $R = \frac{a+b}{2}$ is used the spherical model is very good for 40-60 Grad else the error is smaller than one per cent. A good approximation with $R = \frac{2b+a}{3}$ is near the pole but not for 0-30 degree. The second R can be an alternative but not the third one. Further informations to gravity acceleration on planets can be found at Schröer [4].

References

- [1] Allen's "Astrophysical Quantities", Springer Verlag, 4.edition, 2000
- [2] Lang "Astrophysical Formulae", volume 2, Springer Verlag, 1999
- [3] H.Sieber "Mathematische Tafeln", Klett Verlag, Stuttgart, 3.edition, 1979
- [4] H. Schröer "Theory of orientation - The visual vertical", Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag, Berlin, 2002